

INCREASING CASES OF CHILD SEXUAL EXPLOITATION IN PROVINCE OF SINDH AND MARKDOWN PROSECUTION

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ABSTRACT

Modern technology has advanced humankind and created new connections beyond community building, religions, cultures etc. and since the inventions are made for the betterment and facilitations of human beings are being misused by the criminal minded people for gain. Lust and acquiring wicked desires more rather than its good use in favor of human being, use of children in sex, lust and sex exploitation are also an example of this chain.

It is alarmingly that the children are being abused sexually as to earn gain, or seduced, induced, enticed away or kidnaped to compel for marriage, recent case is abduction of minor Dua-e-Zehra Qazmi, said to be kidnaped from Karachi. Later on recovered from Panjab with her boyfriend Zaheer Anwar, claiming to have exercised her “right of free will marriage”. The said test case along with thousands of similar cases are question mark on the legal definition of kidnapping and abduction. God knows the further tale of this girl in future as if her family, on her said statement terminate relations from her then no body shall be there to support or secure her from any untoward incident.

On the other hand, the State is completely failed to provide safety and safeguard to the families as provided in the Constitution of Pakistan. The investigation and prosecution are also not responding properly after commission of the offences against children. Today we want to see where the problem lies and defects in the investigations and how can we respond.

Keywords: Child Sexual Exploitation, Child Abuse, Child Protection, Child Rights, Sexual Assault, Child Welfare, Child Advocacy, Child Safety, Child Awareness Programs, Sindh Province.

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